

THE IMPORTANCE OF IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING

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Annotation: *The article describes the significance of utilizing multimedia technology in teaching. It deals with some problems in the process of teaching and assessing. Moreover, article includes the role of Web applications in enhancing students' motivation. Nowadays, information communication technology (ICT) has become one of the crucial part of the education that is always emphasized, especially by foreign language pedagogy scholars. The aim of the paper is to introduce the innovative method of assessment using web application. Furthermore, work includes the best examples of Web applications, which is crucial for efficient teaching and assessing.*

Index Terms: *Web application, ICT, motivation, diagnostic assessment, pedagogical diagnostics, digital educational sources*

INTRODUCTION

It is no exaggeration to say that 2020 was one of the most difficult years in the history of humanity. The coronavirus that appeared in Wuhan province of China in December 2019, spread widely in a short period of time and completely changed the way of lifestyle of the people all over the world. Long-lasting lockdown, change in working strategies and ever-increasing risks require radical reformation in every sector. "This is a critical emergency that requires urgent actions, so we address to the global community, particularly individuals, corporations, foundations, governments and other organizations, to come together," said UNICEF Executive Director Henrietta Faure.

The established quarantine measures have become a unique test in almost all sectors of the countries. In addition, in accordance with the decision of the Special Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, all educational institutions in our country

started working from distance from April 1, 2020, and the academic year 2019-2021 completed remotely. As a result of quarantine measures that lasted for almost 7 months, by autumn, the extent of the spread of the coronavirus in our country was controlled, and educational institutions were gradually allowed to continue their activities in the traditional way. Experts, on the other hand, repeat again and again that even though the disease rate of has been curbed, it does not mean that the disease has completely disappeared, and they address to citizens to take safety measures. "I repeat, it is not right to be complacent that the disease has not entered us, to forget the safety protection and hygiene. Precautionary measures are still in practice," said Nurmat Otabekov during an interview with media reporters. For this reason, with the resumption of activity in the fields, it is required partially and in others fully updates in working styles in order to take precautionary measures.

Pedagogues and teachers are striving to improve the quality of education with the help of new methods and approaches that do not harm the health of students and themselves. It is well known that teachers evaluate students' knowledge skills using various approaches. These include mini-tests, written exercises or quizzes. But in today's current situation, it is required to limit face to face contact as much as possible, paper -based assessments can lead to the spread of the virus. In this situation, we recommend an interesting interactive method using ICT teaching .

UNESCO believes that ICT can contribute to the accessibility and the quality of education as well as it is the main toll for the professional development of teachers. In addition, with appropriate policies, technologies and capacities, ICTs can help improve the management, leadership and administration of education.

Information technology has become an integral part of the economy, science, and modern life in general. Therefore, today it is necessary to create a new educational model, which would combine a variety of pedagogical approaches, methods that gives an opportunity for the most complete self-realization of the potential personality.

As knowledge is accumulating at a very fast pace, institutions of higher education often do not supply the needs of the market and employers. For this reason, dynamically developing companies have begun to create special workshops and retraining centers for their specialists. As, this trainings are aimed a quick possible training of employees, it is very highly specialized.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) have become the engine of globalization in the field of education and it provides the greatest opportunities to improve the quality of educational services, as well as the diligence of students and teachers. Especially, implementation of ICT in assessment process is a great chance to motivate students as well as it is the brilliant solution to provide unequivocal policy.

There is a plenty of educational websites such as www.kahoot.com, which are intended to promote friendly competitive atmosphere. First, a teacher must register and have a profile on www.kahoot.com. This site is a convenient tool for organizing

educational processes remotely. "We believe that there should be no restrictions on your ability to learn, no matter when or where you are. Involve students in learning even when you are outside the educational institution...", claims the organizers of the site to encourage everyone to organize a high quality educational process regardless of the circumstances. Not only in the process of distance education, but also by bringing many interesting functions of this site to the audience, it is possible to organize classes interactively, limiting close communication. Moreover, integration of the ICT, as an example of organization of online quizzes and competitions, increase students' enthusiasm towards mastering the science. The only required action is that the teacher should create various tasks in the form of review quizzes on the personal profile on the site. Interestingly, created tasks are implemented to the lesson as a game during the lesson through this site. The question is displayed on a large screen with the help of a projector (Fig. 1). Students determine the answer to the question using the gadget in their hands (phone, tablet, netbook, laptop, etc.) (Figure 2). Each correct answer is evaluated automatically (picture 3) and the statistics of performance is shown on the screen (picture 4). Strikingly, game participants earn points based on the number of seconds they spend to select the correct answer which means that the students are awarded points based on their speed.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

By using this technology in training, we follow the guidelines of the World Health Organization (WHO) on social distancing. It is important to include that at a briefing held in Geneva on July 7, WHO technical director for the prevention and

control of infectious diseases, Benedetta Allegrani, stated that there is evidence that the coronavirus is transmitted through the air. "Airborne transmission of the coronavirus cannot be ruled out in crowded public places, closed and unventilated rooms. In addition, we can create a competitive environment in the educational process and increase the enthusiasm of students to study a lot and independently research the topics covered.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted weakening of teaching cannot be allowed under any circumstances. Therefore, every specialist should strive to organize his classes in accordance with the quarantine rules and improve the quality of education using multimedia technologies. The implementation of multimedia technologies in the assessment process is an important component of teaching, which helps students learn their skills. If students can analyze their performance in the lesson, understand their strengths and weaknesses, they can quickly determine whether they can understand the lesson material or not. It gives them positive motivation and inspires them to achieve their goals and succeed in their field. Knowing their performance in the courses leads to a form of self-evaluation, which allows them to work harder, thereby significantly increasing their quality and level, as well as the effectiveness of the lesson.

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